

Bringing together African and European partners to fight skin-related neglected tropical diseases in Sub-Saharan Africa through an AI-powered mobile app designed for frontline health workers.

Read the press release announcing the launch of SkincAlr

We are delighted to announce the **SkincAlr's first press release**, marking an exciting milestone for the consortium. The release introduces the project to the public, highlighting its mission and outlining the **objectives that will guide SkincAlr over the next five years**. It also details the innovative methodology behind the initiative and the anticipated social benefits that will result from it.

This first publication opens the door for stakeholders, partners and the wider community to **follow the project's progress and stay informed** about its developments. The press release provides information on how to stay connected with SkincAlr, ensuring transparency and engagement throughout the project's lifecycle.

[Read the press release](#)

SkincAfr kick-off meeting in Kenya

From 7 to 10 July 2025, the SkincAfr consortium came together —online and in person— for its **first kick-off meeting, hosted by the Kenya Medical Research Institute (KEMRI)** in Nairobi. Over three days, the consortium aligned on the project roadmap, explored each work package, and laid the groundwork for an ambitious mission: fighting skin-related neglected tropical diseases (NTDs) in Sub-Saharan Africa.

[Read the full article](#)

SkincAfr at the EDCTP Forum

The [EDCTP Forum 2025](#) took place in Kigali, Rwanda, from 15 to 20 June under the theme 'Better health through global research partnerships'. The EDCTP Forum is a biennial event that provides an **international platform for presenting and discussing cutting-edge research** into poverty-related and neglected infectious diseases in sub-Saharan Africa. Although the **SkincAlr** project had only just begun by the time of the Forum, some of its **representatives did not want to miss the opportunity to attend**.

[Read the full article](#)

From vision to action: the SkincAlr origins story

In this series of interviews, we **explore SincAlr's journey from concept to reality**. We also hear from some of the people involved in the project about their vision for achieving our goal over the next five years: bringing together African and European partners to combat neglected tropical skin diseases in sub-Saharan Africa using an AI-powered mobile app designed for frontline healthcare workers.

Gil Sharvit, from HSLU

In this interview, **Gil Sharvit**, Senior AI Researcher at [Lucerne University of Applied Sciences and Arts](#) (HSLU), tells us his thoughts on the project and what he **hopes the future holds for SkincAlr**.

“SkincAlr is one of those few opportunities, as an academic, where you have the chance to actually make a large impact. **This is something that will actually change parts of the world**. The SkincAlr consortium has so many

representatives of the affected countries, and with their knowledge we can have the impact that we plan”.

SkincAlr according to us

In this series, we meet some of the people behind SkincAlr and discover what makes the project so special from the partners' perspective.

Gustavo Hernandez, UPM

We present **Gustavo Hernandez**, Associate Professor at [Universidad Politécnica de Madrid](#) and SkincAlr Project Coordinator. “What I like the most about this project is the nature and devotion of all members. And that **we are all committed to the same goal**”.

Alemtsehay Getachew, AHRI

We present **Alemtsehay Getachew**, dermatologist, physician and researcher at Armauer Hansen Research Institute ([AHRI](#)).

“In sub-saharan Africa we have a shortage of dermatologists. The ratio is very low, so many patients do not have access to them. **I hope to see the SkincAlr app implemented to help us** -the frontline healthcare workers- to early diagnose and detect the skin related tropical diseases”.

Introducing the new SkincAlr website

We are thrilled to announce the launch of the brand [new SkincAlr website!](#) SkincAlr aims to fight skin-related neglected tropical diseases in Sub-

Saharan Africa through an AI-powered mobile app designed for frontline health workers. Our **new site brings:**

- A clear presentation of our mission: to develop an AI-powered mobile tool for frontline health workers, enabling early detection and better surveillance of skin NTDs in Sub-Saharan Africa.
- Insight into the burden of skin NTDs — from scarcity of dermatological services to stigma, underreporting, and health inequality.
- Details of our process and how we combine European and African expertise to create meaningful impact.
- Profiles of our dedicated team and partners driving this initiative forward.
- Easy ways for stakeholders, health professionals, researchers, and supporters to connect, learn, and collaborate.

This website is more than just a digital presence — it's a gateway to sharing knowledge, fostering cross-continental collaboration, and supporting frontline health workers. Explore the [website](#), follow our journey and join us in the fight against skin NTDs!

Visit the SkincAir website!

SkincAir Project

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